

1 **LPS activation of Zbtb32.**

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6 We measured total transcription by microarray in human cells following exposure to a panel of pathogen
7 associated molecular patterns, including R878, MDP, pl:pC, flagellin, and CpG DNA. We demonstrate
8 here that exposure of human cells to lipopolysaccharide (LPS) results in specification activation of *Zbtb32*.

9 GSE44719

10 Citations

11 1. Beaulieu, A.M., Zawislak, C.L., Nakayama, T. and Sun, J.C., 2014. The transcription factor Zbtb32
12 controls the proliferative burst of virus-specific natural killer cells responding to infection. *Nature*
13 *immunology*, 15(6), pp.546-553.
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